

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Infra-Structural Equation Modelling: Sustainably Scaling an Indispensable Open-Source Theory-Testing Infrastructure
Project duration (in months)	48 months

English public summary

Structural equation modelling (SEM) is one of the most powerful, flexible statistical methods available for representing and validating scientific theories. Commercial software packages prevent researchers from adopting fully open-science practices when utilizing SEM. This project improves the quality and expands the scope of the best available open-source SEM package, lavaan, to fully realize its stated goal: “to provide researchers and teachers a free open-source, but commercial-quality package for latent variable modelling”. Accountability and quality-control methods will be implemented sustainably, to ensure taxpayer-funded science is conducted transparently at the highest standards. Open-access education materials will democratize access to this powerful method.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100

Dutch public summary

Structurele vergelijking modellering (SEM) is een krachtige, flexibele statistische methode voor het representeren en valideren van wetenschappelijke theorieën. Commerciële softwarepakketten verhinderen onderzoekers om volledig open-wetenschappelijke praktijken toe te passen. Dit project verbetert de kwaliteit en breidt het toepassingsgebied uit van het best beschikbare open-source SEM-pakket, lavaan, om het gestelde doel volledig te realiseren: “onderzoekers en docenten een gratis open-source, maar commercieel kwaliteitspakket bieden voor latente variabele modellering”. Verantwoordings- en kwaliteitscontrolemethoden zullen op duurzame wijze worden geïmplementeerd (en gecommuniceerd via open-access voorlichtingsmateriaal) om ervoor te zorgen dat door de belastingbetaler gefinancierde wetenschap op transparante wijze volgens de hoogste normen wordt uitgevoerd.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 100

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Structural equation modelling (SEM) is one of the most general frameworks for statistical modelling, subsuming many fundamental methods like regression, ANOVA, causal/path modelling, and factor analysis.

SEM's frequent use across diverse scientific fields makes SEM software a **critical scientific infrastructure**, whose **sustainability is undermined** by high expense and uncertainty about future support. Particularly, the R package **lavaan** is a **critical open-science (OS) infrastructure**, whose nearly 4 million downloads implies saving billions in research funding.

This project is a timely **investment in lavaan's infrastructure**, coinciding with the trend of universities adopting **free open-source software (FOSS)**, even directly supporting development of JASP to replace SPSS. Dozens of R packages already depend on lavaan, including the increasingly impactful JASP package's SEM module, but lavaan's community infrastructure currently lacks organisation. This project will **improve the current infrastructure** by updating lavaan's design to better **support community-driven development** of lavaan and related extensions. Downstream effects of establishing this **sustainable open-SEM infrastructure** include:

- lavaan's capabilities and quality match (and eventually exceed) commercial SEM software,
- more researchers adopt **reproducible/replicable OS practices**.

We facilitate the latter by **adapting an open-source SEM book** for **community contribution**, allowing customization of open-access SEM dissemination for the full spectrum of scientific fields.

Word count SEC31 (max. 200): 199

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

SEM's versatility in representing complex theories as statistical models meets the needs of **dozens of scientific disciplines** (tens-of-thousands of Google-Scholar hits in psychology, education, medicine, physics, chemistry, climate science) and beyond academia to **industry use** (e.g., consumer research, HR analytics, chemometrics, pharmaceuticals, big-tech) and **government** (e.g., educational assessments, survey analysis).

Challenges for SEM users

- Widely used commercial SEM packages are maintained by (nearly) retired professors, **undermining the long-term sustainability** of a critical scientific infrastructure.
- Commercial SEM software is **expensive** (e.g., UvA-FMG spends 7000 €/year on *Mplus* alone).
- Closed-source SEM software **violates^{2,4} the OS principles¹⁰ of transparency, reproducibility, and accountability**.
- The complexity of OpenMx⁶ prevents its widespread use as a FOSS alternative.

The open-source R package lavaan⁸ is user-friendly, highly popular, and capable of fitting standard models. **Without funding or community support**, the lavaan maintainer struggles to meet demands of researchers who need features only available in commercial software (if at all).

Challenges for research software engineers (RSEs)

The **lavaan authors need a sustainable way** to keep up with **community demands for transparency** and advanced SEM features. The maintainer has made information accessible to enable RSEs from the *lavaan ecosystem^{3,9}* to build extensions that **meet their dynamically evolving scientific needs**.

A more sustainable solution requires:

- restructuring lavaan's codebase to **prioritize modularity**,
- developing training tools to **standardize community involvement**.

As the growing RSE community diversifies lavaan's capabilities, the user base will grow, which increases the scientific

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community's dependence on lavaan, thus reinforcing our bargaining position to solicit (institutional) financial support for long-term sustainability (Section 5.1).

Challenges for SEM educators/learners

No FAIR platform exists for user/developer communities (e.g., lavaan's [Google group](#) is restricted in China).

By developing **open-access educational materials** and a fully available **support structure**, this project brings an OS infrastructure to scale for the most widely used multivariate data analysis technique.

Word count SEC32 (max. 300): 300

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

This project will follow OS principles¹⁰ and enable researchers to conduct more OS, making "scientific process more transparent, inclusive, and democratic". The project has **4 work packages** (WPs; details in [Section 4.1](#)), each of which **aligns with specific OS principles**:

WP1: By [refactoring](#) lavaan's source code to prioritize "[modularity](#)", this project enables **sustainable long-term development** by **worldwide collaborators *without* financial barriers**. Using C++ to implement these modules, lavaan will achieve the computationally efficiency of commercial software, while surpassing its **transparency** and **reproducibility**.

WP2: We will modernize lavaan's accountability infrastructure by using **open-source** packages for automated testing¹¹ and documentation^{12,13}, to ensure **transparent** quality-control. **Freely available training materials** will enable lavaan contributors to maintain similar standards for lavaan extensions, becoming an **infrastructure for sustainable accountability**.

WP3: Build an accessible infrastructure to facilitate **more community development and maintenance**, adhering to the **OS principles¹⁰ of collaboration and participation** by enabling SEM users to become SEM developers^{3,9}. **Freely available training tools** (e.g., web pages, video tutorials) will demonstrate how researchers can use the developer platform GitHub to:

- a) contribute new features to lavaan itself, with clear rules for recognition in the [documentation](#) and [website](#)
- b) program their own lavaan extensions,

Following the [Stan](#) community's example, a [Discourse](#) platform will enable the emerging **open-SEM community** (researchers, developers, educators) to **self-organize** and **self-govern** as the community grows. The **community moderation** feature will provide a safer, more open forum than the antiquated [SEMNET listserv](#), to **build an infrastructure of community support** with **easily accessible** and searchable archives.

WP4: An **open-access SEM textbook** (developed on GitHub using **open-source software**, published on Zenodo) will be generalized for researchers in **any scientific field** who use **any open-source software** (e.g., [semopy](#) in Python). **Open-access** tutorials will demonstrate how the **community can contribute** their own chapters, thus becoming an **infrastructure for community education**.

Word count SEC33 (max. 300): 300

3.4 Access policy

Referring to the FAIR-software¹ recommendations:

1. The lavaan package will continue to be maintained (and automatically tested) on GitHub as a publicly **accessible** repository, governed by lavaan co-authors who review community contributions (see Section 5.2). There is no cost, requiring only an internet connection for anyone to access it.
 - Many lavaan-ecosystem packages (listed as “reverse dependencies”) are also hosted on GitHub
 - Training tools (WP3) demonstrating standardized contribution practices will be shared via Zenodo.
2. lavaan is licensed under the GNU GPL, protecting everyone’s right to **reuse, redistribute, and adapt**.
3. lavaan is registered in the well-known/maintained and FAIR-compliant comprehensive R archive network (CRAN).
4. The R function citation() provides a peer-reviewed publication⁸ and authorship of the currently installed lavaan version.
5. The open-access book (WP4) is licensed under CC-BY-SA on GitHub to ensure versatile adaptability. Different compiled versions will be uploaded to Zenodo for persistent identifiers.

Word count SEC34 (max. 150): 146

3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem

Our project scales the already essential lavaan infrastructure for universities to transition away from commercial closed-source software. Modularizing lavaan’s codebase has important implications for the **(inter)national open-source research-software ecosystem**. Version-control on GitHub (another international infrastructure) enables reusing lavaan’s codebase for other FOSS (not limited to SEM).

Our project contributes to **realizing EOSC Objective 2.1C**: “developing tools and services [for the] reuse of research data and software.” Archived with a DOI on the FAIR-compliant international OS infrastructures CRAN, lavaan (and its ecosystem) achieves **EOSC Objectives 2.1 A and 2.2 H**: “ensuring that research software is traceable, citable, and discoverable.”

Nationally, this project addresses **TDCC-SSH’s Challenges 1, 2, and 6** and **TDCC-LSH’s software & tools challenge**, also building on prior initiatives for open-software infrastructure like the ADORE toolkit, FAIR Software Checklist, and Research Software Directory. To ensure compliance, our advisory board includes Anna-Lena Lamprecht (established the FAIR software concept CITE 2022) and Jeroen Ooms (rOpenSci developer and creator of R-universe). Finally, our project contributes to the goal of the **Dutch Reproducibility Network** to increase the quality of efficiency of research in the Netherlands, as well as the large-scale SSH component of the EOSC (SSHOC-NL, in collaboration with CLARIAH and ODISSEI).

Word count SEC35 (max. 200): 198

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

The project consists of 4 work packages designed to (WP1&2) raise lavaan's quality to commercial-level standards while maintaining open-source/OS values, (WP3) build a sustainable open-SEM community, and (WP4) create a framework for community-contributed open-access SEM education.

WP1: Refactor lavaan—restructure internal processes while preserving lavaan's user friendliness. Our design philosophy will prioritise modularity and composability, to streamline maintenance and community contribution, with valuable direct and downstream effects:

- **Increased computational efficiency.** Modularity allows the most computationally intensive components of lavaan to be rewritten in C++, resulting in noticeably reduced estimation time for complex models.
- **Improved extensibility.** Modularity enables RSEs from the growing lavaan community to contribute more easily, reliably, and sustainably (WP3) to the lavaan ecosystem. The lavaan team itself will prioritize extensions requiring numerical integration (e.g., full support for multilevel SEM: random slopes/variances, categorical variables), support for high-dimensional data (i.e., neuroimaging, genomics), and support for non-numerical data (i.e., functional data, text, shapes, or graphs).
- A more competitive lavaan will encourage greater uptake from users who already seek open-source alternatives to *Mplus*, resulting in **open-source values becoming the norm** in SEM.

All development will be conducted on GitHub by current lavaan authors and postdocs (to be hired at UvA). M. Jiménez will work part-time (at VU) on the latent package's interface, for lavaan to utilise some of its C++ modules (e.g., to estimate SEM with latent classes).

WP2: Modernize lavaan's accountability infrastructure. Maintaining high-quality standards for open-source SEM software requires transparency, predictability, and a sustainable software-development process.

- a. **Quality-control tests** will be designed to automatically (re)validate "visible" features and "invisible" background calculations at every step of the development cycle.
- b. Package **documentation** will be made more extensive and integrated with software development to ensure it remains clear, accurate, and up-to-date with every released version.

Since lavaan's 2010 inception, R packages have become available to streamline the package-development process by automating an R package's documentation¹², website¹³, and quality-control testing¹¹, some of which have been adopted by lavaan-ecosystem packages (e.g., blavaan⁵). WP2 will be conducted on GitHub while refactoring lavaan (WP1). F. Schubert will supervise a full-time research assistant, to integrate best practices for package testing/documentation into lavaan's development process.

WP3: Mobilize a growing community already eager to contribute to the lavaan ecosystem^{3,9}. This project organizes the existing lavaan community's activity, consolidates it with other open-SEM communities, and provides an accessible community-support platform.

- a. **Set community standards** for continuing lavaan-ecosystem development. The standards will be implemented for WP1&2 and described transparently (WP3) in extensive documentation, demonstrating how to apply the same standards when contributing to lavaan or writing lavaan extensions, resulting in **open-access tutorials** to inform the community.
- b. **Consolidate infrastructures for community support.** Following Stan's demonstrated success, a Discourse platform will be built to replace lavaan's Google group (restricted in China) as a user-support platform, resulting in a consolidated digital space for related SEM communities (e.g., blavaan, the obsolete SEMNET mailing list⁷). The Discourse platform will have dedicated spaces for developer communities and lavaan governance.

Software, documentation, and quality-control standards will be communicated in open-access tutorials written for WP3, provided on lavaan's website. Open-science community leader C. van Lissa will coordinate outreach with the Discourse community and the wider open-source software community.

WP4: Develop an infrastructure for community education.

- a. **Reorganize an open-source SEM book** (developed on GitHub) to have a software-agnostic core. To demonstrate the book’s adaptability, M.Garnier-Villarreal will contribute chapters about Bayesian analysis, demonstrating sustainable community contribution (new chapters/sections).
 - b. Coapplicants from psychology, sociology, and health sciences will **write case-study booklets** to accompany the core book with example lavaan analyses. To demonstrate versatility, K.-J. Kan will adapt at least one case-study using the open-source semopy package for Python.
 - c. J.D. Karch will further **develop (on GitHub) a graphical user interface (GUI) for lavaan**, to include all features described in WP4b booklets. Karch will create video tutorials to facilitate widespread adoption of lavaan, demonstrating how to obtain a case-study’s lavaan results with lavaangui.
- M. Verdam, S. Jak, and T.D. Jorgensen will coordinate WP4-a&b (prepare core book, peer-review co-applicants’ contributions) and co-author an open-access tutorial to inform the SEM community about how to utilise and contribute—C. van Lissa will also facilitate community outreach.

Timeline for Work Projects

(Sub)projects	Year			
	2026	2027	2028	2029
WP1	refactor lavaan		develop extensions	
WP2-a		Visible-output tests	Background-calculation tests	
WP2-b		Exhaustively document existing features	Document new features, write vignettes	
WP3-a	Set...		...publish standards	
WP3-b			Build Discourse community	
WP4-a			Organize core book	Contributor tutorial
WP4-b				Write/review case-studies
WP4-c			Complete lavaan-GUI	
Sustainability plan			Initiate OpenSEM-NL, Solicit institutional support	

Word count SEC 41 (max. 750): 750

4.2 Team composition

Co-applicants with extensive experience in R programming, FAIR software development, and SEM education were selected from diverse scientific backgrounds (e.g., psychology, education, economics, sociology, neuroscience, medicine, and health-related quality of life).

Work Project(s)	Initial(s) Surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
WP1	T.D. Jorgensen	UvA	lavaan co-author, SEM education and consultation	Main applicant: project manager, WP1 leader, consultant WP2, book co-author & peer reviewer (WP4)
	Y. Rossee	Ghent	R, C++, lavaan founder	Subcontractor and cooperation partner: software developer WP1, consultant WP2
	M. Jiménez	VU	R, C++, latent-variable modeling	Consulting programmer WP1
	(To hire)	UvA	R, C++	Postdoc lavaan programmers (WP1)
WP2	F. Schuberth	UT	Maintains R package cSEM (lavaan ecosystem)	WP2 leader
	(To hire)	UT	Experience with R	Research assistant for WP2
WP3	C. van Lissa	TU	Open-access SEM book author; chair of OS Community Tilburg (formerly of OS Community Utrecht); board member of OSCNL	Coordinator of community development (e.g., outreach, organize Discourse subcommunities, consultant about community programming-standards instructions)
		Discourse		Third-party contract to develop community hub (WP3)
WP4	M. Verdam	Leiden	SEM book co-author	WP4 coordinator (SEM book), peer-reviewer, Contributes health-related quality of life case-study to WP4
	S. Jak	UvA	SEM book co-author	WP4 co-author & peer-reviewer
	J.D. Karch	Leiden	SEM, (lavaan)GUI designer	lavaangui development for WP4
	K.-J. Kan	UvA	SEM, Python	Contributes Python case-studies to WP4
	M. Garnier-Villarreal	VU	(Bayesian) SEM, blavaan contributor	Contributes Bayesian chapter(s) & case-study to WP4
	B. Grandfield	UU	SEM education	Contributes psychology case-study to WP4
		Maastricht	SEM	Contributes medical-science case-study to WP4
(To hire)	UvA	Organizational skills	Student assistant (administrative assistance with community outreach, book coordination, etc.)	
Sustainability	R. Kievit	Radboud-UMC	SEM application and education, OS	Outreach for long-term sustainability, visits institutions to solicit funding
Advisory board	J.K. Vermunt	Tilburg	LatentGOLD founder	Advise about sustainability issues for latent-variable modeling software
	E.J. Wagenmakers	UvA	JASP founder	Advise about soliciting institutions to fund long-term sustainability
	J. Ooms	rOpenSci, R-universe	Lead Infrastructure Engineer at rOpenSci	Advise about FAIR FOSS
	A.-L. Lamprecht	Potsdam, FONDA	Chair of Software Engineering	Advise about FAIR FOSS
	G. Leckie	Bristol	Co-director Centre for Multilevel Modeling	Advise about initiating analogous Centre for SEM

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 348

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Fail to find postdocs with sufficient programming experience	Likelihood: low/medium Impact: high	R skills are common, C++ less so, but consultants Y. Rosseel and M. Jiménez have C++ experience to facilitate a motivated postdoc's on-the-job learning. Advisor E.J. Wagenmakers will advise how he attracted programmers for JASP.
Community resists new standards for lavaan contribution/extension	Likelihood: low Impact: medium	Short-term: free instructional materials convincingly demonstrate the advantages of adherence to proposed standards. Long-term: Add community representatives to governance.
Generative AI largely replaces quantitative expertise	Likelihood: low Impact: medium/high	Demonstrate added value of human expertise. The role of AI in software development is instead likely to be positive (e.g., useful to debug code).
GitHub's (Microsoft's) business model changes in response to U.S. instability	Likelihood: Low Impact: Medium	Migrating to an <u>alternative to GitHub</u> (e.g., GitLab, hosted by UvA) would be inconvenient but feasible.
R packages used for WP2 cease to be maintained	Likelihood: Low Impact: Low	Source code is available to reuse (GPL)
WP3 prevented from proceeding without successfully establishing standards in WP1&2	Likelihood: low Impact: high	Define standards (WP3) prior to refactoring lavaan, so WP1 proceeds with standards in mind.
Lose funding for Discord	Likelihood: high Impact: low	attracting funding, or transfer the built Discourse site to university server
Fail to secure institutional financial support	Likelihood: high Impact: low	Without funding, lavaan can accomplishing much like it does now. But advisor Wagenmakers will share how he convinced <u>institutions to support JASP</u> .

Word count SEC43 (max. 250): 247

4.4 Budget

Total Personnel requested: € 1,236,816.90
Total Material/IT requested: € 263,183.10
Total budget requested: € 1,500,000.00

4.5 Budget justification

The **largest personnel costs** are for research software engineers (RSEs) with sufficient expertise programming in R and C++ to carry out WP1&2 tasks:

- Main applicant (WP1 leader) and postdoctoral researchers to refactor and extend lavaan with C++.
- WP2 leader and assistant to enhance documentation and testing.

The **largest material cost** is for lavaan founder Y. Rosseel to facilitate successful completion of WP1&2.

Personnel costs will ensure sufficient time for project tasks by reducing teaching for:

- T. Jorgensen to lead WP1 and coordinate with Y. Rosseel, F. Schubert, and [latent](#)-package developer M. Jiménez.
- F. Schubert to lead WP2 and coordinate with lavaan co-authors.
- C. van Lissa and R. Kievit to devote time to community organization and outreach (WP3, sustainability plan).
- M. Verdam to coordinate WP4 (assisted by co-authors): organize core textbook, write the first case-study to use as a template, and develop instructional material for future contributors.
- J.D. Karch to finish developing the lavaan GUI for WP4.
- New book contributors to write new case-studies/chapters.

A student assistant will be hired to help with menial organizational tasks associated with WP3 & WP4.

Other material costs cover (inter)national travel for:

- hackathons, to troubleshoot WP1&2 complexities, accelerate progress, and coordinate upcoming tasks;
- conference visits to disseminate lavaan updates (WP1&2), book (WP4), and emerging community (WP3);
- visiting (inter)national institutions to promote FOSS for SEM and solicit long-term financial support;
- initiating a lavaan-user-group conference.

Additionally, our Discourse subscription will begin as an Enterprise plan, to support migrating decades of valuable posts from SEMNET and (b)lavaan Google groups to a modern community forum. We will downgrade to a [Standard/Business plan](#) (as needed) for subsequent years.

Finally, we will publish 2 [open-access tutorials in the SEM journal](#), the fees for which will likely [be waived](#)—if not, some funds could be redirected from conference travel/organization.

Word count SEC45 (max. 300): 297

4.6 Impact plan

Scientifically, WP1&2 will democratize access to the most advanced SEM features, including high-quality community support (WP3), enabling researchers from various disciplines to transparently, reproducibly, and easily apply cutting-edge SEM techniques, thereby enhancing research quality. Additionally, methodologists will achieve a much greater impact because they can easily integrate their methods into the most popular FOSS for SEM, which will be facilitated by modularity (WP1) and community support (WP3). Improved software testing (WP2) will improve lavaan's accountability and, consequently, the reliability of the many research findings based on it.

Societally, commercial-quality FOSS for SEM facilitates more equitable scientific practices by reducing dependency on costly proprietary software and expanding participation opportunities for underfunded research communities worldwide. The open-source textbook (WP4) complements this by eliminating costs for educational materials, providing high-quality, open-access resources, enhancing teaching quality to benefit both students and educators.

For **businesses**, FOSS for SEM allows companies to direct finite resources to innovation and application rather than [proprietary software licenses](#) (WP1) or [commercial education/training material](#) (WP4). A [report by the ERC](#) demonstrated the downstream impacts of FOSS, both realized (€65,000,000,000 benefit in 2018) and projected (10% increase in FOSS would increase GDP by 0.4%, with 600 new start-ups).

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 196

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan.

Software infrastructure

Rather than hosting lavaan's source code on the founder's personal repository, the restructured lavaan (**WP1 outcome**) repository will be hosted more sustainably on a [GitHub organization](#) account, owned by lavaan co-authors. GitHub organizations are free of cost, until 100.000 members/repositories are exceeded, which is not foreseen. Automated testing/documentation (**WP2 outcomes**) will be built sustainably using open-source software, which can be used without cost in perpetuity. Instructional materials developed for WP3 will make lavaan sustainable even without lavaan's authors, although their experience will provide necessary expertise as the growing community becomes self-sustaining.

Education infrastructure (WP4 outcome)

The open-access book will remain publicly available on GitHub, licensed for reuse and adaptation to specific needs.

Community support (WP3 outcome)

After deliberately growing lavaan's already large, active community (>4000 [Google-group](#) members), sustaining it could eventually require **community participation in lavaan's governance**, similar to other FOSS communities (e.g., [Stan](#), [ggplot2](#)). To this end, we will form a **national committee (OpenSEM-NL)**, chaired by the lead applicant. **Representatives from each Dutch University** (8 already represented in our team) will engage local SEM/lavaan users to disseminate WP1&2 improvements and encourage contributions—maximizing impact by sharing how to fully exploit lavaan's features.

Our community's Discourse platform will have dedicated communication spaces for software developers/contributors, researchers using SEM, novices learning SEM, educators teaching SEM, OpenSEM-NL activities, etc. We can offset the perpetual cost of a [Standard/Business plan](#) by transitioning to a university server. Alternatively, we can solicit funding or recruit the [SEM journal](#)'s owner to sponsor the Discourse platform, as a tax write-off for charitable donation.

Financial support

Although community involvement (WP3 outcome) makes perpetual funding unnecessary for this project to continue, ongoing financial support would ensure long-term sustainability and maximize impact by maintaining a rapid pace of development to meet dynamically evolving OS needs.

- Our faculty liaison (R. Kievit) and OpenSEM-NL representatives will liaise with **colleagues, university librarians, and software managers** to discuss replacing proprietary SEM tools (*AMOS, Mplus*) with FAIR and free alternatives.
- **Staff support** will provide leverage to solicit institutional/university financial support, by showing the direct (financial savings) and indirect (scientific rigour, transparency) benefits of transitioning to lavaan.

This model has been **successfully deployed** in the Netherlands and abroad: Universities are [supporting JASP](#) to replace SPSS.

Scaling-up lavaan enables an **emerging academic business model**, inspired by the successful [Centre for Multilevel Modelling](#). By initiating an analogous Centre for SEM:

- OpenSEM-NL representatives can proactively solicit **support from colleagues applying for grants**, to prioritize developing features needed for proposed research.
- **Consultation and education services** can provide additional revenue streams.

This sustainability strategy will ensure long-term impact by consolidating and capitalizing on SEM expertise in The Netherlands, making it central to the future of worldwide OpenSEM development.

Word count SEC51 (450): 449

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

Lavaan is a well-established user-friendly R package for advanced multivariate statistical analysis with a focus on models containing latent variables. Lavaan can be used to fit and perform a wide variety of models and analyses, including regression models, path analysis, exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis, principal component analysis, canonical correlation analysis, structural equation models, and growth curve models.

The main target audiences are methodological researchers, applied researchers, and teachers.

- As open-source software, lavaan offers methodological researchers the possibility to implement and evaluate their ideas. In addition, lavaan offers methodologists the opportunity to make their ideas openly accessible and thus increase their reach.
- For applied researchers from various fields—including Psychology, Neuroscience, Public Health, Medicine, Sociology, Educational Research, Marketing Research, Management research, Information Systems Research, Ecology, Construction Research, Engineering, and Human Resources—lavaan offers a free solution to conduct their analyses. Since lavaan is syntax-based, its use also facilitates the reproducibility of published studies.
- Finally, lavaan offers a free solution for teachers who use SEM (or special cases of it) in their classes. This has at least two advantages: (i) lavaan can be used free of charge during courses, and (ii) students can use lavaan after their graduation without buying any licenses.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

Lavaan is developed in a [public GitHub repository](#). GitHub is a software development platform built on the open-source version-control software Git. GitHub is specifically designed to enable collaborative software development and version control during software development. In this project we will continue to use GitHub for the development of lavaan. As a result, changes to the lavaan codebase will continue to be tracked.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

All versions of lavaan will continue to be publicly available via GitHub. In addition, each new official release will be made publicly available via the [Comprehensive R Archive Network \(CRAN\)](#). CRAN lists relevant metadata, provides the binaries and source code, gives access to older package versions published on CRAN, and provides a DOI.

Furthermore, we will make the lavaan package available in the [Research Software Directory](#), a directory developed by the Netherlands eScience Center for sharing research software. This will further increase lavaan's visibility and thus contribute to the expansion of the lavaan community.

As common for R packages, lavaan is licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL), specifically GPL 2 or higher. This means that users, including lavaan community members can use, modify and distribute lavaan without any payment. Similarly, any derivative of the lavaan code must be shared under the same or equivalent license terms. Consequently, the GPL ensures that lavaan and its enhancements will remain open and accessible in the future.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

As is common for R packages, users can use the `citation()` command to get the citation for lavaan, which reads for the current GitHub version as follows:

Rosseel Y., Jorgensen T. D., De Wilde L. (2025). lavaan: Latent Variable Analysis. R package version 0.6-20. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.lavaan>

Rosseel, Y. (2012). lavaan: An R Package for Structural Equation Modeling. Journal of Statistical Software, 48(2), 1-36. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v048.i02>

As can be seen, two sources are listed. First, the lavaan software including the lavaan maintainer and the current two lavaan co-authors (with the current lavaan version indicated), and second, it presents the canonical reference for lavaan.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

User documentation:

All functions exported for direct user access are documented. The documentation includes:

- a brief description of the function,
- how to use the function,
- a description of the arguments on which the function depends,
- a more detailed description of the function,
- a description of what the function returns,
- a list of references to sources referenced in the documentation,
- a “See also” section with links to other relevant functions/packages, and
- a section of concrete examples showing how to use the function.

The latest documentations can be found [here](#).

The canonical 2012 article about [lavaan](#) gives an overview of lavaan's basic user interface, and the current lavaan [website](#) offers a small number of [examples](#) that show users how to perform types of analyses in lavaan that became available since the 2012 publication.

In this project these examples will be added to the lavaan vignettes. In addition, the vignettes will be automatically converted into a website (e.g., using GitHub pages and the [R package pkgdown](#)), thus increasing the accessibility of the lavaan user documentation. Moreover, our how-to-contribute guide (see Point 6 of the software management plan) will contain guidelines on how to contribute enhancements to lavaan including examples. Therefore, this project is expected to stimulate the development of more examples by the lavaan community. Finally, there is already a lot of “third-party” material about lavaan [available on the Internet](#). We hope that our how-to-contribute guidelines will encourage others to contribute directly to lavaan.

Developer documentation

To support the development of lavaan, a concise [description of its main internal steps](#) is provided. This gives future developers an insight into how lavaan works and facilitates contributing. Moreover, the lavaan code includes code comments that provide context for others looking at the code.

In this project we will revise this description if necessary and make it more accessible via the new lavaan website. Moreover, lavaan is an R package and licensed under the GNU GPL 2 or higher, which permits others to use, modify, and distribute lavaan's codebase. This is mentioned on the GitHub repository and in the metadata of lavaan on CRAN. The same applies to lavaan's dependencies, which are other R packages (see Section 8 of the SMP).

Installation requirements

Lavaan is an R package. Therefore, it runs within the R environment. Moreover, it only depends on other R packages (and not on software distributed outside the R environment). Therefore, if R can be installed, lavaan can be run as well.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

In order to facilitate contribution, this project will update and extend lavaan's current contribution guidelines:

- **Code of Conduct:** Currently, lavaan uses the [Contributor Covenant Code of Conduct](#), which has been specifically proposed as a code of conduct for open-source communities. It consists of a set of rules, norms, and responsibilities that aim at ensuring a welcoming and safe environment for collaboration. We will adhere to this code of conduct.

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- Governance model: Currently, there is no explicit governance model for lavaan contributions. Implicitly, lavaan follows a founder-leader governance model. In this project, the governance model will be reviewed (and revised as necessary) to clearly define roles and their responsibilities in workflows (e.g., how to become a contributor, who is responsible for ‘merging’ pull requests on GitHub, and who decides in case of conflicts).
- How-to-contribute guidelines: Currently, lavaan provides a brief description of how to contribute to lavaan. In this project, we will enrich [this description](#) (e.g., adding coding standards, adding a description for contributing testing and examples).
- Contributor role taxonomy: Contributions to lavaan can differ, which needs to be recognized. In this project, we will therefore follow the contributor role taxonomy suggested in the [utils package](#), which is based on the [MARC code list for relators](#) and commonly used to recognize contributors in R package development. This taxonomy ascribes different roles to contributors depending on the extend of contribution and involvement. In case it turns out during this project that this taxonomy is not broad enough, we will look for other best practices and extend the taxonomy.

The new governance model, together with the code of conduct, the how-to-contribute guidelines, and the contributor role taxonomy will be documented and made available on the lavaan GitHub repository and the new lavaan website. Moreover, we will make explicit how contributions are handled according to the (new) governance model.

7. How will your software be tested?

Currently, lavaan is tested in several ways. First, lavaan is unit tested, i.e., the output of certain functions is tested against predefined values, and the output of certain functions is compared between the current and the previous lavaan version. Second, certain lavaan results are compared with those of Mplus. However, these tests do not use up-to-date testing facilities such as the R package [testthat](#), nor are they publicly available or automated. The only automated test is the [R CMD checks](#), which are run on various operating systems using GitHub Actions. Passing these checks is the bare minimum of tests that an R package must pass before it can be released on CRAN.

In this project, we will automate the existing tests and make them publicly available using the latest R solutions. In addition, we will implement more unit tests to increase the unit test coverage of the codebase. Ultimately, such tests should also be implemented by the lavaan community and accompany future lavaan enhancements. This will also make it easier to detect unintended consequences of changes to the lavaan codebase. Moreover, we will implement automated reverse dependency testing (e.g., using the R package [revdepcheck](#)) during this project to ensure that new lavaan releases do not break other packages that depend on lavaan. Furthermore, once style guidelines have been agreed upon, tests will be implemented to check that functions conform to these guidelines (e.g., using the [R package lintr](#)). Since we aim to integrate the documentation of lavaan functions directly into the R code using the [R package roxygen2](#), roxygen’s internal tests will also ensure consistency of the parameter documentation. In addition, roxygen 2 allows to add tests to the documentation (e.g., using the [R package doctest](#)). Finally, coverage tests will be implemented to verify the amount of codebase that is actually tested (e.g., using the [R package covr](#)).

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

Currently, lavaan is released under the GNU GPL 2 or higher and depends solely on other R packages released on CRAN:

- methods (part of R core and therefore released under the GNU GPL license)
- stats4 (part of R core and therefore released under the GNU GPL license)
- stats (part of R core and therefore released under the GNU GPL license)
- utils (part of R core and therefore released under the GNU GPL license)
- graphics (part of R core and therefore released under the GNU GPL license)
- MASS (GNU GPL license)
- mnormt (GNU GPL license)
- pbivnorm (GNU GPL license)
- numDeriv (GNU GPL license)
- quadprog (GNU GPL license)

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The GNU GPL permits to use, modify, and distribute the codebase of a software. In addition, the GNU GPL is compatible with CRAN.

Since this project also involves rewriting components of the lavaan code in C++, which will require C++ libraries, we will carefully consider their licenses to avoid conflicts. If necessary, a possible solution might be to separate the code based on 'problematic' C++ libraries into a separate R package with a different license.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

Lavaan will be packaged and distributed via CRAN, the official repository for R packages. In addition, this project aims to make lavaan available in the [Research Software Directory](#). Moreover, development versions of lavaan will be made available via the lavaan GitHub repository.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

Currently, lavaan functions that are exported for direct user access are supported by documentation and examples for different analyses are provided on the lavaan website. This project will allow us to improve the lavaan documentation for users. For instance, improving the consistency of the documentation, including examples directly in the documentation, and creating a new lavaan website that makes the documentation, including more detailed explanations, available to a wider audience. In addition, this project allows us to develop collaboration guidelines, including a governance model to facilitate the contribution process, including the contribution of examples. In this way, the lavaan community can also directly support lavaan users.

Moreover, lavaan users seeking support can currently ask lavaan-specific questions in the [lavaan Google group](#). So far the Google group has more than 4,000 members with more than 5,000 questions. Currently these questions are mainly answered by the three lavaan authors. During this project, we will migrate the lavaan Google group to [Discord](#), following the success story of the Stan community, and the lavaan authors will continue to answer the user questions. As it is expected that the number of questions will increase with the growth of the lavaan community, the goal of this project is also to further involve the lavaan community in answering user questions. For this purpose we will define roles and responsibilities within the lavaan community to facilitate this support structure. We hope that by the end of the project we will have mobilized the lavaan community to such an extent that this support structure will be self-sustaining.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

A goal of the project is to mobilize and expand the lavaan community in order to have a support community that is able to maintain and develop lavaan. Because this will take some time, the current lavaan maintainer and authors, as well as the leaders of work packages 1 and 2, will maintain lavaan for the duration of the project until a sufficient support community is established.

Although community maintenance is the envisioned goal regarding the long-term maintenance of lavaan, the lavaan authors will seek institutional support/funding. Lavaan is being developed as free open-source software to replace commercial software such as [IBM SPSS Amos](#) and [Mplus](#). Switching to lavaan can therefore save institutions money that they can (partially) spend on lavaan development and maintenance. An example in this respect is [JASP](#).

Furthermore, the lavaan authors will offer grant support, which will be promoted via the new lavaan website. If grant writers need certain features/analyses for their projects, they can contact the lavaan authors to see if this is feasible. After a green light, grant writers can reserve a budget in their project that can be used for lavaan maintenance/development. We will mention this opportunity on the new lavaan website.

In addition, the lavaan authors will try to attract further funding to ensure the long-term maintenance of lavaan. Similarly, lavaan supporters can already make donations on the lavaan website. Although this is not very successful at the moment, we hope that as the lavaan community grows, it will become easier to raise money in this way, so that the lavaan maintainer has resources available to continue maintaining lavaan.

Section 6: References

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Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.